
MODULAR DVORETZKY, TYPE-COTYPE, KHINCHIN-KAHANE AND GROTHENDIECK INEQUALITY PROBLEMS

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Abstract: We recently formulated Modular Dvoretzky, Type-Cotype, Khinchin-Kahane and Grothendieck Inequality problems in the Appendix of [arXiv:2302.03718v1]. For the sake of wide accessibility we give a separate treatment of them.

Keywords: Dvoretzky Theorem, Type-Cotype, Khinchin-Kahane Inequality, Grothendieck Inequality, C*-algebra, Hilbert C*-module.

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1. MODULAR PROBLEMS

Our first kind of problems come from the Dvoretzky theorem [7–10, 13, 14, 27–33, 36, 37]. Let \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} be finite dimensional Banach spaces such that $\dim(\mathcal{X}) = \dim(\mathcal{Y})$. Remember that the Banach-Mazur distance between \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} is defined as

$$d_{BM}(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}) := \inf\{\|T\|\|T^{-1}\| : T : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y} \text{ is invertible linear operator}\}.$$

For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let $(\mathbb{R}^n, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$ be the standard Euclidean Hilbert space.

Theorem 1.1. [1, 18] (*John Theorem*) *If \mathcal{X} is any n -dimensional real Banach space, then*

$$d_{BM}(\mathcal{Y}, (\mathbb{R}^n, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)) \leq \sqrt{n}.$$

Theorem 1.2. [1, 6] (*Dvoretzky Theorem*) *There is a universal constant $C > 0$ satisfying the following property: If \mathcal{X} is any n -dimensional real Banach space and $0 < \varepsilon < \frac{1}{3}$, then for every natural number*

$$k \leq C \log n \frac{\varepsilon^2}{|\log \varepsilon|},$$

there exists a k -dimensional Banach subspace \mathcal{Y} of \mathcal{X} such that

$$d_{BM}(\mathcal{Y}, (\mathbb{R}^k, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)) < 1 + \varepsilon.$$

Let \mathcal{A} be a unital C*-algebra with invariant basis number property (see [12] for a study on such C*-algebras) and \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{F} be finite rank Banach modules over \mathcal{A} such that $\text{rank}(\mathcal{E}) = \text{rank}(\mathcal{F})$. Modular Banach-Mazur distance between \mathcal{E} and \mathcal{F} is defined as

$$d_{MBM}(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{F}) := \inf\{\|T\|\|T^{-1}\| : T : \mathcal{E} \rightarrow \mathcal{F} \text{ is invertible module homomorphism}\}.$$

Given a unital C*-algebra \mathcal{A} and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, by \mathcal{A}^n we mean the standard (left) module over \mathcal{A} . We equip \mathcal{A}^n with the C*-valued inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle : \mathcal{A}^n \times \mathcal{A}^n \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ defined by

$$\langle (a_j)_{j=1}^n, (b_j)_{j=1}^n \rangle := \sum_{j=1}^n a_j b_j^*, \quad \forall (a_j)_{j=1}^n, (b_j)_{j=1}^n \in \mathcal{A}^n.$$

Hence norm on \mathcal{A}^n is given by

$$\|(a_j)_{j=1}^n\| := \left\| \sum_{j=1}^n a_j a_j^* \right\|^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad \forall (a_j)_{j=1}^n \in \mathcal{A}^n.$$

Then it is well-known that \mathcal{A}^n is a Hilbert C*-module. We denote this Hilbert C*-module by $(\mathcal{A}^n, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$.

Problem 1.3. (Modular Dvoretzky Problem) *Let \mathcal{A} be the set of all unital C*-algebras with invariant basis number property. What is the best function $\Psi : \mathcal{A} \times (0, \frac{1}{3}) \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ satisfying the following property: If \mathcal{E} is any n -rank Banach module over a unital C*-algebra \mathcal{A} with IBN property and $0 < \varepsilon < \frac{1}{3}$, then for every natural number*

$$k \leq \Psi(\mathcal{A}, \varepsilon, n),$$

there exists a k -rank Banach submodule \mathcal{F} of \mathcal{E} such that

$$d_{MBM}(\mathcal{F}, (\mathcal{A}^k, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)) < 1 + \varepsilon.$$

A particular case of Problem 1.3 is the following conjecture.

Conjecture 1.4. (Modular Dvoretzky Conjecture) *Let \mathcal{A} be a unital C*-algebra with IBN property. There is a universal constant $C > 0$ (which may depend upon \mathcal{A}) satisfying the following property: If \mathcal{E} is any n -rank Banach module and $0 < \varepsilon < \frac{1}{3}$, then for every natural number*

$$k \leq C \log n \frac{\varepsilon^2}{|\log \varepsilon|},$$

there exists a k -rank Banach submodule \mathcal{F} of \mathcal{E} such that

$$d_{MBM}(\mathcal{F}, (\mathcal{A}^k, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)) < 1 + \varepsilon.$$

Our second kind of problems come from the type-cotype theory of Banach spaces [1, 5, 19, 20, 24–26, 38]. Let \mathcal{H} be a Hilbert space, $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Recall that for any n points $x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathcal{H}$, we have

$$(1) \quad \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n \in \{-1, 1\}} \left\| \sum_{j=1}^n \varepsilon_j x_j \right\|^2 = \sum_{j=1}^n \|x_j\|^2.$$

It is Equality (1) which motivated the definition of type and cotype for Banach spaces.

Definition 1.5. [1] *Let $1 \leq p \leq 2$. A Banach space \mathcal{X} is said to be of (Rademacher) type p if there exists $T_p(\mathcal{X}) > 0$ such that*

$$\left(\frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n \in \{-1, 1\}} \left\| \sum_{j=1}^n \varepsilon_j x_j \right\|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq T_p(\mathcal{X}) \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \|x_j\|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \quad \forall x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathcal{X}, \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Definition 1.6. [1] Let $2 \leq q < \infty$. A Banach space \mathcal{X} is said to be of **(Rademacher) cotype q** if there exists $C_q(\mathcal{X}) > 0$ such that

$$\left(\sum_{j=1}^n \|x_j\|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \leq C_q(\mathcal{X}) \left(\frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n \in \{-1, 1\}} \left\| \sum_{j=1}^n \varepsilon_j x_j \right\|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}, \quad \forall x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathcal{X}, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Let \mathcal{E} be a (left) Hilbert C^* -module over a unital C^* -algebra \mathcal{A} , $n \in \mathbb{N}$. We see that for any n points $x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathcal{E}$, we have

$$(2) \quad \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n \in \{-1, 1\}} \left\langle \sum_{j=1}^n \varepsilon_j x_j, \sum_{k=1}^n \varepsilon_k x_k \right\rangle = \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x_j, x_j \rangle.$$

Problem 1.7. (Modular Type-Cotype Problems) *Whether there is a way to define type (we call modular-type) and cotype (we call modular-cotype) for Banach modules over C^* -algebras which reduces to Equality (2) for Hilbert C^* -modules?*

Problem 1.8. *Whether there is a notion of type and cotype for Banach modules over C^* -algebras such that Kwapien theorems holds?, In other words, whether following statements hold?*

- (i) *A Banach module \mathcal{M} over a unital C^* -algebra \mathcal{A} has modular-type 2 and modular-cotype 2 if and only if \mathcal{M} is isomorphic to a Hilbert C^* -module over \mathcal{A} .*
- (ii) *If \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} are Banach modules over a unital C^* -algebra \mathcal{A} of modular-type 2 and modular-cotype 2, respectively, then a bounded module morphism $T : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ factors through a Hilbert C^* -module over \mathcal{A} .*

Problem 1.9. (Modular Khinchin-Kahane Inequalities Problems) *Whether there is a Khinchin-Kahane inequalities for Banach modules over C^* -algebras which reduce to Equality (2) for Hilbert C^* -modules?*

Our third kind of problems come from Grothendieck inequality [1–4, 11, 15–17, 21, 34, 35].

Theorem 1.10. [1, 3, 4, 11, 15, 35] **(Grothendieck Inequality)** *There is a universal constant K_G satisfying the following: For any Hilbert space \mathcal{H} and any $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, if a scalar matrix $[a_{j,k}]_{1 \leq j \leq m, 1 \leq k \leq n}$ satisfy*

$$\left| \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n a_{j,k} s_j t_k \right| \leq 1, \quad \forall s_j, t_k \in \mathbb{K}, |s_j| \leq 1, |t_k| \leq 1,$$

then

$$\left| \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n a_{j,k} \langle u_j, v_k \rangle \right| \leq K_G, \quad \forall u_j, v_k \in \mathcal{H}, \|u_j\| \leq 1, \|v_k\| \leq 1.$$

Problem 1.11. (Modular Grothendieck Inequality Problem - 1) *Let \mathcal{A} be the set of all unital C^* -algebras. Let \mathcal{E} be a Hilbert C^* -module over a unital C^* -algebra \mathcal{A} . Let \mathcal{A}^+ be the set of all positive elements in \mathcal{A} . What is the best function $\Psi : \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}^+$ satisfying the*

following property: If $[a_{j,k}]_{1 \leq j \leq m, 1 \leq k \leq n} \in \mathbb{M}_{m \times n}(\mathcal{A})$ satisfy

$$\left\langle \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n a_{j,k} s_j t_k, \sum_{p=1}^m \sum_{q=1}^n a_{p,q} s_p t_q \right\rangle \leq 1, \quad \forall s_j, t_k \in \mathcal{A},$$

$$s_j s_j^* = s_j^* s_j = 1, \forall 1 \leq j \leq m, t_k t_k^* = t_k^* t_k = 1, \forall 1 \leq k \leq n,$$

then

$$\left\langle \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n a_{j,k} \langle u_j, v_k \rangle, \sum_{p=1}^m \sum_{q=1}^n a_{p,q} \langle u_p, v_q \rangle \right\rangle \leq \Psi(\mathcal{A}, m, n), \quad \forall u_j, v_k \in \mathcal{E},$$

$$\langle u_j, u_j \rangle = 1, \forall 1 \leq j \leq m, \langle v_k, v_k \rangle = 1, \forall 1 \leq k \leq n.$$

In particular, whether Ψ depends on m and n ?

Problem 1.12. (Modular Grothendieck Inequality Problem - 2) Let \mathcal{A} be the set of all unital C^* -algebras. Let \mathcal{E} be a Hilbert C^* -module over a unital C^* -algebra \mathcal{A} . Let \mathcal{A}^+ be the set of all positive elements in \mathcal{A} . What is the best function $\Psi : \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}^+$ satisfying the following property: If $[a_{j,k}]_{1 \leq j \leq m, 1 \leq k \leq n} \in \mathbb{M}_{m \times n}(\mathcal{A})$ satisfy

$$\left\langle \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n a_{j,k} s_j t_k, \sum_{p=1}^m \sum_{q=1}^n a_{p,q} s_p t_q \right\rangle \leq 1, \quad \forall s_j, t_k \in \mathcal{A}, \|s_j\| \leq 1, \forall 1 \leq j \leq m, \|t_k\| \leq 1, \forall 1 \leq k \leq n,$$

then

$$\left\langle \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n a_{j,k} \langle u_j, v_k \rangle, \sum_{p=1}^m \sum_{q=1}^n a_{p,q} \langle u_p, v_q \rangle \right\rangle \leq \Psi(\mathcal{A}, m, n), \quad \forall u_j, v_k \in \mathcal{E},$$

$$\|u_j\| \leq 1, \forall 1 \leq j \leq m, \|v_k\| \leq 1, \forall 1 \leq k \leq n.$$

In particular, whether Ψ depends on m and n ?

We believe strongly that Ψ depends on \mathcal{A} .

Remark 1.13. Modular Bourgain-Tzafriri restricted invertibility conjecture and Modular Johnson-Lindenstrauss flattening conjecture have been stated in [22, 23].

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